

Research article (Featured theme: Geolinguistic approaches to linguistic patterns in Asia and Africa)

Introduction: Geolinguistic approaches to linguistic patterns in Asia and Africa

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Abstract: This introduction provides some background on the geolinguistic approaches to data used by the contributors to this special issue, who were all involved in the project of making the three-volume *Linguistic Atlas of Asia and Africa*. The papers focus on clarifying the distributions of linguistic *patterns*—not linguistic *matter*—in data from Asian and African languages, including sibling term systems, numeral systems, alignment, and stop series.*

Keywords: *Linguistic atlas of Asia and Africa*; geolinguistic approach; linguistic pattern; linguistic matter

The contributors to this special issue were all involved in the project to make the *Linguistic Atlas of Asia and Africa (LAAA)*, volumes *I*, *II*, and *III* (Suzuki et al. 2022, 2023, and Fukushima et al. 2023). The project applied geolinguistic approaches to the linguistic variation in Asia and Africa. Experts on specific languages or language groups collected the data and made linguistic maps of the items of interest for each language or language group, using ArcGIS online. All of the project’s participants were guided to understand the expected system types/elements. In addition, the maps the individual researchers created employed the same sets of symbols (assigned beforehand) in most cases, which made it possible to envision the distributions of system types when the maps of different languages were combined.

For the mapping, each language or language group was assigned one of seven colors, as shown in Table 1.

FUKUSHIMA, Chitsuko. 2024. Introduction: Geolinguistic approaches to linguistic patterns in Asia and Africa. *Studies in Geolinguistics* 4: 142–144. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13948601>

* This work was supported by Tokyo University of Foreign Studies, April 2020–March 2023 ILCAA Joint Research Project: Studies in Asian and African Geolinguistics (jrp000256), with Mitsuaki Endo as coordinator; and JSPS KAKENHI grant number JP19K00555. I also thank the members of the 2020–2023 project.

Table 1 The language groups and colors (made by Satoko Shirai)

Language group	Color	Language group	Color
Ainu	Red	Korean	Light blue
Andamanese and language isolates (South Asia)	Black	Kra-Dai	Navy
Austroasiatic	Green	Kx'a (Kalahari Basin Area)	Light blue
Austronesian	Orange	Mongolic	Green
Caucasian	Light blue	Niger-Congo	Navy
Chukotko-Kamchatkan	Black	Nilo-Saharan	Green
Dravidian	Red	Semitic	Brown
Hmong-Mien	Orange	Sinitic	Red
Indo-Aryan and Nuristani (South Asia)	Navy	Tibeto-Burman	Brown
Iranian	Orange	Tungusic	Orange
Japonic	Green	Turkic	Light blue
Khoe-Kwadi (Kalahari Basin Area)	Brown	Tuu (Kalahari Basin Area)	Orange
		Uralic	Light blue

Linguistic geography was once been called “word geography,” and it is often regarded as centering on the history of words. And of course, *LAAA* includes lexical items: animal vocabulary [Rat/Mouse, Chicken, Horse, Dog, Wolf, and Bear] and crop terms [Wheat, Broomcorn Millet (*Panicum miliaceum*), Foxtail Millet (*Setaria italica*), Barnyard Millet (*Echinochloa* Species), Taro, and Yam]. Nevertheless, linguistic geography can also focus on phonological, morphological, or semantic variation. This special issue features four items from the *LAAA*: two lexical systems, those of sibling terms and numerals; one grammatical item, specifically grammatical relations or alignment; and one phonological item, that is, stop series. Note that while the first three systems were assigned symbols for each system type as mentioned above, the stop series were not assigned symbols beforehand.

These items have one common characteristic: they are concerned with what Matras and Sakel (2007) called “linguistic patterns,” in contrast to “linguistic matter.” These terms are useful to explain distinct types of contact-induced changes. When languages share “linguistic matter,” it is due to “the replication of morphological material from the source language” (841), which is usually called “borrowing” and is the result of language contact. You can find many examples of shared linguistic matter in the maps of lexical items, such as those representing the distributions of the animal and crop vocabulary mentioned above. On the other hand, the sharing of “linguistic patterns” refers to “the replication of *usage* patterns from a model language” (841; emphasis added). For example, the sibling term systems occur across geographic space in

linguistic patterns; a type of sibling term system used in a source language is introduced to the surrounding area, and the words of the recipient language are used to occupy the parts of the system. If, for instance, a brother/sister system is introduced from a source language, two local words may be adopted to mean “brother” and “sister.” This could also apply to numeral systems. Usage patterns can include grammatical and phonological patterns as well; hence, the maps of alignment and stop series patterns are included as part of this issue’s featured theme. They show interesting distributions, which in fact prove that they are also linguistic patterns.

The featured papers all employed the same method to create the maps they include, as follows. The existing maps of each language or language family, made by the individual language/language group experts, were superimposed on each other, again using ArcGIS online. The resulting map included all of the attested types of linguistic patterns of the system in question. In order to show the distribution of each type, the maps of other types were deleted; then a map of each type was produced. The featured articles provide the maps along with the authors’ interpretations of the information represented in the maps.

The maps thus produced show the distributions that we might otherwise never have seen and the experts’ interpretations clarify the contributions to our understanding of the linguistic geography of Asia and Africa.

References

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Publication history

Date received: 31 August 2024

Date accepted: 17 September 2024